

PREDICTION OF MODULUS OF INJECTION MOLDED CF/LCP THIN PLATES

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SUMMARY

The modulus of the injection molded carbon fiber (CF)/ liquid crystal polymer (LCP) thin plate was estimated by the Cox formula and by laminate theory based on the fiber orientation and distribution of the modulus of the LCP in the thickness direction. It was verified that the prediction method suggested in this paper was valid to estimate the modulus of thin injection molded CF/LCP plates.

Keywords: Liquid crystal polymer, Carbon fiber, Modulus, Fiber orientation, Injection

INTRODUCTION

LCP molded parts have been used for electronic applications because of their high strength and stiffness, superior damping properties and superior processability, especially their low viscosity. An injection molded thin plate of Liquid Crystalline Polymer (LCP) has a unique structure and unique mechanical properties. Because of the shear force and the elongation force generated in injection molding, especially near of the mold wall, LCP undergoes alignment, and consequently it exhibits anisotropic properties^[1-7]. In order to control this anisotropy in an industrial process, fillers and fibers are used. The effects of gate design and injection speed on the multi-layered structure, fiber orientation, mechanical properties and coefficient of linear expansion in injection molded carbon fiber reinforced LCP (CF/LCP) thin plate have been clarified^[8-11]. Moreover, the method of estimating the modulus has been examined, taking account of the layered structure and fiber orientation^[12].

The most important characteristic of an injection molded CF/LCP thin plate is that it has a layered structure, in which the fiber orientation and length vary from one layer to another. Thus its fracture behavior in bending could be likened to a laminated composite such as carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin and so on. In order to estimate the modulus of thin plates fabricated by CF/LCP, the concept of lamination should be used. However, the distribution of modulus in the thickness direction has not yet been quantitatively measured in an injection molded thin plate.

In this study, the properties of carbon fiber reinforced LCP (CF/LCP) plates were investigated. The CF/LCP thin plates were injection molded. The LCP and CF/LCP

plates were sliced at 0.1mm intervals, and the moduli of the sliced specimens were measured with a Dynamic Mechanical Spectrometer (DMS). The modulus of the CF/LCP thin plates was calculated by the Cox formula and by laminate theory based on the fiber orientation and distribution of the modulus of the LCP in the thickness direction. The calculated values were compared with the experimental ones, and the effect of the carbon fibers on the orientation of LCP was examined.

LAYER STRUCTURE OF CF/LCP THIN PLATES

Experimental Procedures

The pelletized materials studied were (i) a neat LCP (VECTRA A950, Polyplastics Co.) and (ii) carbon fiber reinforced /LCP or CF / LCP (VECTRA A230, Polyplastics Co., $V_f = 30\text{wt}\%$, average fiber length about 0.2mm). The two kinds of pellets were mixed under dry conditions to obtain 20wt% of carbon fiber content. The neat LCP and reinforced LCP specimens were injection molded for the experiments.

A plate cavity mold with a film gate was used. The dimensions of the plate were 55 (width) x 70(length) x 1.0 (thickness) mm, as illustrated in Fig.1. A reciprocating screw injection molding machine with a hydraulic accumulator system (V110/75V, Sumitomo Heavy Machinery Co.) was used. The injection molding conditions were cylinder temperature 320 °C, mold temperature 100 °C and injection speeds 150mm/s ($68\text{cm}^3/\text{s}$). Specimens were cut out from the plates in the parallel (machine direction, MD) and perpendicular (transverse direction, TD) to machine direction, as illustrated in Fig.1.

In order to measure modulus by slicing the specimens, MD and TD specimens at the center of the plates of CF/LCP and LCP were sliced at intervals of 0.1mm by means of a microtome (SM2500S, Leica Micro Systems Co.). The microtome was a special apparatus, which can slice relatively large specimens with at a fixed interval in the thickness direction. The standard slicing conditions were as follows. The speed was 5mm/s in the MD and TD specimens of CF/LCP, 3mm/s in the MD, and 10mm/s in the TD of LCP. The tool angle was 40°. The elastic modulus of each sliced specimen was measured by a viscoelastometer (DMS210 Seiko Electronics Industry) at a frequency of 1Hz.

A detailed evaluation of fiber orientation was performed for each sliced specimen of CF/LCP. The surface of each sliced specimen was polished, and optical microphotographs of the polished surface were taken. Image processing was applied to the center region (3x4mm) of the molded plate as indicated by the filled square in Fig.1. The measuring routine in the image processing known as “measurement of maximum diameter” was used. The image processing technique enables the determination of the total number of fibers, their length and angle to a given axis of each fiber.

The conversion of the picture to monochrome was performed to distinguish the fiber clearly, and here the threshold was an important parameter i.e. determining the grayscale cutoff point that yields a good binary contrast enhancement. The fiber volume fraction was taken as the ratio of the area of the white region to that of the total area. The fiber volume fraction changed with changes in the threshold. It was confirmed that under the appropriate threshold, the total number of fibers are

representative of the actual number, and the calculated fiber volume fraction coincided with the actual fiber volume fraction.

Fig.1 Plate cavity mold and cutting position of specimen.

Experimental Results

Fig.2 shows the relationship between the modulus (measured by using sliced specimens) and depth from the surface in CF/LCP. The depth from the surface of the sliced specimen in the molded plates was expressed as the ratio of the distance from the surface to the plate depth. 0% means the surface of the molded plate, and 50% means the center of the thickness. The validity of this method of using sliced specimens was verified by establishing the modulus of the molded plate.

Fig.2 Distribution of modulus in the thickness direction of CF/LCP.

In order to verify that the injection molded CF/LCP can be treated generally as a laminated composite, the modulus of the whole specimen was calculated by laminate beam theory, using a different modulus for each slice, and compared with the experimental value measured by the three point bending test. It was assumed that the

MD and TD specimens were symmetrical in the thickness direction. The formula for laminate beam theory is

$$EI = \sum E_i (A_i z_{0i}^2 + I_{0i}) - z_0^2 \sum E_i A_i \quad (1)$$

where EI is the bending rigidity of the laminated plate, E_i is the modulus of the i th layer, A_i is the cross section area of the i th layer, z_{0i} is the distance between any axis and the neutral axis of the i th layer, I_{0i} is the second moment of area against the neutral axis of the i th layer, and z_0 is the distance between any axis and neutral axis of laminate plate.

For both the MD and TD specimen, the calculated values (MD= 28.8GPa, TD= 3.6GPa) were in good agreement with the experimental values (MD: 28.1GPa, TD: 3.4GPa). From this result, it is considered that there was no relaxation effect involving residual stress etc. affecting the elastic properties when the specimen was sliced. It was confirmed that the injection molded CF/LCP could be treated generally as a laminated composite.

Figs.3 and 4 show the relationship between the modulus and the depth from the surface in CF/LCP and LCP. In the MD specimen of CF/LCP, as shown in Fig.3, the modulus decreased from 0% (surface) to 50% (center). In the TD specimen, the modulus was constant up to 20% of depth, and then increased between 20% and 50%. On the other hand, the modulus of LCP decreased in the MD specimen and increased in the TD specimen with increasing depth, as shown in Fig.4.

Fig.3 Distribution of modulus in the thickness direction of MD specimen of CF/LCP. (a)MD specimen, Bending modulus of the plate: 28.1GPa, (b)TD specimen, Bending modulus of the plate: 3.4GPa.

Fig.4 Distribution of modulus in the thickness direction of LCP.

PREDICTION OF MODULUS OF CF/LCP

Prediction Method

The modulus of the sliced MD and TD specimens was predicted by Cox and by laminate theory. Fig.5 shows a flowchart for the prediction of modulus. In order to calculate the bending modulus of a molded plate by laminate beam theory, the moduli of sliced specimens were calculated by laminate theory. E_{Li} which was the modulus of a unidirectional composite in the 0° direction and E_{Ti} , the modulus in the 90° direction were calculated from the Cox formula as follows:-

$$E_{LTi} = \eta_0 \eta_{Li} E_f V_{fi} + E_{mi} (1 - V_{fi})$$

$$\eta_{Li} = \sum \alpha_j \cdot \eta_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j \left\{ 1 - \left(\tanh \frac{1}{2} \beta_i \ell_j \right) / \frac{1}{2} \beta_i \ell_j \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta_i = \left\{ \frac{2G_{mi}}{E_f r^2 \ln(R_j/r)} \right\}^{1/2}$$

Here, E_{LTi} is the modulus in the 0° and 90° directions, E_f , E_{mi} are the moduli of the fiber and the matrix, V_{fi} is the fiber volume fraction and η_0 is the coefficient of fiber orientation. ℓ_j is the fiber length, G_{mi} is the shear modulus of the matrix, R_i is half the distance between fibers and r is the radius of the fibers. Parameters with an i, j suffix were calculated in each sliced specimen, because these values change in the thickness direction.

In order to evaluate β_i , G_{mi} was calculated by means of equation (3):-

$$G_{mi} = \frac{4}{E_{m45^\circ}} - \left[\frac{1}{E_{mLi}} + \frac{1}{E_{mTi}} - \frac{2\nu_L}{E_{mLi}} \right] \quad (3)$$

where E_{mLi} , and E_{mTi} were measured on the sliced non-reinforced LCP specimen.

Next it was assumed that the arrangement of fibers was a hexagonal close-packed structure with the radius of the fiber R_i calculated by the following equation,

$$R_i = r \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3} \cdot V_{fi}}} \quad (4)$$

When η_{Li} was calculated, the effect of the distribution of fiber length and direction was considered. Fiber length in a sliced specimen was measured by an image processing system for every 0.01mm, and in the case that the total fiber length was 100%, the ratio α_j was calculated from the ratio of the sum of the fiber lengths in each sorted fiber length to the total fiber length. Then each η_{ij} in the sorted fiber length was calculated. The coefficient of fiber length in each sorted fiber length α_j was multiplied by η_{ij} , and the integration of $\alpha_j \cdot \eta_{ij}$ in each sorted fiber length was η_{Li} . The coefficient of fiber orientation η_0 was 1 for an orientation angle L(0°), and 0 for T(90°). The fiber length distribution was obtained by image processing of the sliced specimen, and the modulus of LCP was used for E_{mi} , as shown in Fig.4. Consequently, E_{iL} and E_{iT} were calculated.

Fig.5 Flowchart for prediction of modulus.

Moreover, the distribution of fiber volume fractions in the thickness direction was considered in the prediction of the modulus. The distribution of the fiber volume fraction in the CF/LCP plate is shown in Fig.6. This distribution was reflected in equation (2).

Fig.6 Distribution of fiber volume fraction in thickness direction of CF/LCP.

Next, laminated theory was applied to calculate the modulus of each layer. Laminate theory is the prediction formula for the elastic property of a laminated plate, which in this case is a unidirectional plate laminated with the fiber orientation angle in various directions. The relationship between the stress and strain of the plate with an angle was expressed by equation (5):-

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

\bar{Q}_{ij} is a transformed stiffness tensor, σ , τ are stress, ε , γ are strain. Assuming that the strain in each layer was constant, the relationship between the stress and the strain of the laminated plate was expressed by equation (6) as follows.

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n [\bar{Q}_{ij}] * t_k$$

Here, N is the total stress, n is the number of layers, t_k is the ratio of the thickness of each laminate to the total thickness. E_i was calculated by equation (7) as follows, for unidirectional loading.

$$E_i = \frac{A_{11}A_{22}A_{66} - A_{11}A_{26}^2 + 2A_{12}A_{16}A_{26} - A_{12}^2A_{66} - A_{16}^2A_{22}}{t(A_{22}A_{66} - A_{26}^2)} \quad (7)$$

The fiber length and fiber orientation angle were measured by image processing for each fiber, and fiber orientation was evaluated. Fig.7 shows (a) an optical

microphotograph of the polished surface and (b) the result of evaluation of fiber orientation by image processing. The abscissa shows the fiber orientation angle relative to the flow direction of the resin every 10°. The ordinate axis shows the coefficient of fiber orientation, which is the ratio of the sum of the fiber lengths for each fiber orientation angle to the total fiber length. It was assumed that each sliced specimen with its distribution of fiber orientation angles was a laminate plate consisting of a unidirectional plate for each fiber orientation angle. The coefficient of fiber orientation for each orientation angle was converted into the ratio of the thickness of the unidirectional plate to the total thickness in laminated plate. The modulus of each layer was calculated by laminate theory using the modulus of the unidirectional plate and the thickness, in the above mentioned method. The modulus of the molded plate was calculated by laminate beam theory using the calculated value obtained by that theory. Laminate beam theory is shown as equation (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Coefficient of Fiber Orientation (\%)} \\
 &= \left[\frac{\text{Sum of fiber length in each fiber orientation angle}}{\text{Total fiber length}} \right] \times 100 \\
 &= \text{Rate of thickness of unidirectional plate in laminated plate}
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig.7 Fiber orientation and distribution of fiber orientation.

Prediction of Results

Fig.8 shows the relationship between the calculated modulus, the experimental modulus for the MD and TD specimen and the depth from the surface for specimens made at the low injection speed. In the case of the MD specimen, the calculated value was similar to the experimental value while the region around the surface was an exception. In the TD specimen, the calculated value showed a similar tendency to the experimental one, although the values were lower around the surface and increased towards the center.

Table 1 shows the bending modulus obtained by experiment and by the suggested prediction method in MD and TD specimens. Calculated values were in good

agreement with experimental values. As a result, the accuracy of the method for predicting the modulus was established.

Fig.8 Comparison of distribution of calculated and experimental modulus in CF/LCP plates.

Table 1 Bending modulus obtained by experiment and suggested prediction method in CF/LCP.

Bending Modulus (GPa)			
MD		TD	
Exp.	Cal.	Exp.	Cal.
28.1	25.2	3.4	2.9

CONCLUSIONS

The structure and distribution of carbon fiber reinforced LCP injection molded plates were investigated using a slicing technique with slices cut at 0.1mm intervals. Moreover the modulus of the CF/LCP thin plate was estimated by the Cox formula and by using laminate theory based on the fiber orientation and modulus of each LCP layer.

The injection molded CF/LCP can be treated in general as a laminated composite, and the distribution of moduli in the injection molded CF/LCP can be evaluated by the slicing technique. Moreover, it was shown by evaluation of the fiber orientation and modulus of the sliced specimen that the fiber orientation contributed to the difference in the modulus in the thickness direction. It was verified that the prediction method suggested in this paper is a valid one for estimating the modulus of the injection molded CF/LCP thin plate.

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